

MADRASAH HEAD STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING MAN TEACHERS' PERFORMANCE (QUALITATIVE DESCRIPTIVE STUDY AT MAN KOTAWARINGIN TIMUR AND MAN 1 PULANG PISAU)

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Abstrak

In carrying out his main duties as a top manager at a madrasah, the head of the madrasah aliyah often faces various problems in efforts to improve teacher performance and competency. This research aims to describe and analyze the strategic management of madrasah heads in improving the performance of MAN teachers. The qualitative research method adopts Terry's management theory, Wheelen & Hunger's strategic management, and Davies' performance theory. The results of this research found that the madrasa's environmental analysis was based on the principles of Hunger and Wheelen. In environmental analysis, the madrasa has based a rational logic value system, which is based on data owned by the institution even though the database is still incomplete. Strategic planning in improving the performance of MAN teachers in these two MANs is by the concept of Hunger & Wheelen using SWOT analysis. It has also formulated a vision, mission, goals, objectives, strategies and policies. While the strategic implementation of Madrasah Heads at these two MANs has implemented the strategic management evaluation principles from Hunger & Wheelen regarding the availability of human resources, they still need more motivation to develop and improve their performance. The strategic control of madrasah heads in improving teacher performance is carried out with guidelines on the main duties and functions of madrasah heads as managers and supervisors. The strategic evaluation of madrasah principals in improving teacher performance has been carried out based on teacher performance assessment.

Keywords: Strategic Management, Madrasah Principals, And Teacher Performance

A. INTRODUCTION

The competencies of madrasah aliyah heads include personality competencies, managerial competencies, entrepreneurial competencies, supervisory competencies and social competencies (Suhardi et al., 2020). The head of an aliyah madrasah has a strategic role in forming an educational environment that supports development to improve teacher performance (Triono et al., 2023). The head of an aliyah madrasah must also have various competencies as a form of ability or authority in carrying out tasks based on certain concepts and theories (Susanto, 2022). The head of the madrasah aliyah is the highest person in the institution who has the task of leading and being

responsible for everything related to the institution so that the goals of the institution are realized.

According to (Pranata et al., 2023), a madrasa head must have basic managerial skills, namely: 1) technical skills (technical skills), 2) human skills (human skills), and 3) contextual (conceptual) skills'. According to (Muflihah & Haqiqi, 2019), the role of the school principal is that schools must manage and develop all school components through administration, management and leadership activities. To support and implement the competency of the head of the Madrasah Aliyah by established standards, he must have strategic management capabilities (Panjaitan, 2022). According to (Nizar, 2022), strategic management is a science combining management functions in the context of making strategic organizational decisions to achieve organizational goals effectively and efficiently.

The head of an aliyah madrasah, as an educational leader, has duties and responsibilities in developing teachers in the madrasah he leads (Mustafida, 2021). The position of the head of the Madrasah Aliyah in developing teacher performance is considered to be very effective because he is seen to understand better the needs felt in the field (Mukhtar et al., 2023). One of the strategies that needs to be carried out to maintain the existence of madrasahs is that the head of the aliyah madrasa can realize leadership in the entire educational process (Muflihah & Haqiqi, 2019). The success of education in madrasah aliyah is determined by the ability of the head of the madrasah aliyah to influence, guide, mobilize and motivate teachers involved in the agreed educational goals (Masykur et al., 2022).

The strategic role of the head of Madrasah Aliyah as a manager is, of course, carrying out the stages of the management function, which can be understood as a process of utilizing the potential resources that exist within the organization, as well as other sources through a process of planning, organizing, mobilizing and controlling which is carried out systematically (Masruhah & Djubaedi, 2023). Therefore, the success of a manager or leader in managing an organization depends on his ability to utilize the members of the organization to carry out their duties, whether strategic, technical or operational tasks (Masdiana et al., 2022).

One of the main tasks of the head of an aliyah madrasah is to improve teacher performance or performance, also known as work performance, work performance, or results of work implementation. According to (Maruhawa et al., 2022), performance management is prepared using rankings and determined after a performance assessment. The rating indicates the quality of performance or competency displayed by the employee by selecting the level on the scale closest to the rater's view of how well the employee performs (Komsiyah, 2022). To achieve increased performance as a professional, hard work and consistency are required by the head of the Madrasah Aliyah, especially in carrying out his duties as a manager and as a supervisor of learning that takes place in the madrasah (Islahuddin et al., 2021). One approach that is assumed to assist the implementation of the duties of the head of Madrasah Aliyah in carrying out his managerial duties is the strategic management approach (Fuadi et al., 2021).

The head of the aliyah madrasah is responsible for managing the madrasah he leads, especially in formulating plans and assessing the implementation of what has been planned (Idrus et al., 2023). Strategic management focuses on integrating management, marketing, finance or accounting, production or operations, research and development, and computer information systems to achieve organizational success (Fajar, 2021). In carrying out his main duties as a top manager at a madrasah, the head of the madrasah aliyah often faces various problems, including several aspects of the areas he is working on, namely the curriculum, students, facilities and infrastructure. Apart from that, problems arise from efforts to improve teacher performance and competency by achieving the madrasa vision, madrasa mission and madrasa goals (Fahmy et al., 2021).

Improving the quality of schools needs to be planned and implemented by the work goals and targets to be achieved based on the vision, mission and goals set within the specified period (Chostholani et al., 2021). This condition requires various remedial efforts to improve the quality of education. Another problem also often occurs when school principals cannot rely on the provisions set out in standardized education programs. This situation will result in the implementation of school programs becoming rigid and less adapted to the situations and conditions that occur in the school.

Teacher performance will be optimal if the head of the Madrasah Aliyah can organize and guide the teachers well so that the teachers can carry out their duties with full responsibility, pay attention to the interests and welfare of their subordinates, and have no complaints in carrying out their daily duties and obligations (Amirudin et al., 2022). According to (Akib & Salnawati, 2022), variable indicators of teacher performance include a) work quality, b) teacher speed/accuracy, c) initiative in work, d) workability, and e) communication. Therefore, there is a need for strategic management of madrasah heads in improving the performance of state madrasah aliyah (MAN) heterogeneous teachers, consisting of differences in ethnicity, language, skin colour, gender, age differences and different educational backgrounds.

According to (Mukhtar et al., 2023), teachers' performance measures can be seen from their sense of responsibility in carrying out their mandate, profession, and moral responsibility. This will be seen in their sense of responsibility in preparing all teaching equipment before the learning process. Apart from that, the teacher has also considered the methodology that will be used, including the educational media tools that will be used and what assessment tools will be used in the evaluation (Masruhah & Djubaedi, 2023).

According to (Maruhawa et al., 2022), school principals who carry out democratic leadership will make teachers perform their duties well. According to (Idrus et al., 2023), to improve the quality of education, school principals must have competence and professionalism in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. The competence and professionalism of school principals can be implemented well, one of which is supported by the use of strategic management in implementing school programs, which will have an impact on improving the quality of education (Hoque et al., 2020)). Thus, only some people can become a school principals. Adequate provision is required in the form of

knowledge and skills according to the main tasks and functions in efforts to improve quality by national education standards (Akib & Salnawati, 2022).

According to (Triono et al., 2023) educational institutions will experience improvement if the subject of education, namely the school principal, can manage strategic management well. Strategic management is directed at developing madrasah educational institutions so that they are truly efficient, becoming part or vehicle for change in the lives of Muslim communities in Indonesia, especially through improving the administrative quality of education providers in madrasahs, the quality of personnel or human resources, the quality of madrasah operational management, as well as the quality of learning and madrasa graduate. Apart from that, in strategic management, several components are interrelated and interconnected with each other, which move towards achieving organizational goals, such as components, vision, mission, strategic goals of the organization, operational goals, as well as the implementation of management functions in the form of planning, organizing functions, control and evaluation and feedback functions.

The quality of education will only be successful with the right strategy to improve the quality of all components; problems that occur include teacher professionalism, graduate competency standards, effective learning, and programs that do not support quality achievement. One effort to improve quality is through applying strategic management to determine the right strategy to improve the quality of education.

Based on the problems explained previously, this research aims to find out how internal and external environmental analysis, strategic planning, strategic implementation, strategic control and strategic evaluation of Madrasah Aliyah principals improve the performance of MAN Kotawaringin teachers. Timur dan MAN 1 Pulang Pisau.

B. RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a qualitative approach by exploring data sources with participant observation and in-depth interviews (Shaver, 2021). The qualitative approach also has broad and in-depth insight into the field of education that will be researched; namely the strategic management of madrasah aliyah heads with variables of internal and external environmental analysis, strategic planning, and strategic implementation. Strategic control and strategic evaluation in improving teacher performance at MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau.

1. Data Collection Technique

In research, systematic and standard data collection techniques exist to obtain the required data (Shaver, 2021). Data collection is a very important step in the scientific method because, in general, the data collected is used, except for exploratory research, to test hypotheses that have been formulated.

The data collection techniques in this research are as follows:

a. Interview

The interview technique takes several informants along with the things that will be explored to complete the data for preparing this research. Some of the information that the researcher will extract from the participants is 1) information about the strategic management of the head of the aliyah madrasah at MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, 2) information about teacher performance at MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau.

Interviews are a method of collecting data related to the strategic management of madrasah aliyah heads in improving teacher performance, which can be obtained directly from information sources, namely, the Head of the Madrasah Education Section of the Kotawaringin Timur Regency Ministry of Religion and the Head of the Madrasah Education Section of the Pulang Pisau Regency Ministry of Religion, Madrasah Supervisor at the Regency Ministry of Religion Kotawaringin Timur and Ministry of Religion Pulang Pisau Regency, head of madrasah aliyah at MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, teacher at MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau.

b. Observation

Observation is used to find out something about a phenomenon. Observations are usually done by reviewing, supervising and researching an object until obtaining valid data (ref). The objects of observation in this research are:

- The condition of MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau.
- The availability of infrastructure.
- Various forms of objects can be observed.

Observations made when carrying out active activities in the madrasah environment.

c. Documentation

The results obtained from documentation techniques in this research can be in the form of madrasa head work program documents, Teacher Competency Test assessment results, madrasah head performance assessment results, Teacher Performance Assessment, attendance, learning journals, learning administration, SKP teachers for ASN teachers, photos of teacher coaching, official meetings, minutes of meetings related to teacher coaching related to the strategic management of madrasah aliyah principals in improving teacher performance at MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau.

2. Data Collection Instrument

Developing instruments is an important step in the research procedure pattern. The instrument functions as a tool for collecting the necessary data. The form of the instrument is related to interview and observation collection techniques. An overview of research data collection is described through a grid, and data collection instruments from this research are presented in the table below.

No	Research purposes	Research Indicators	Data source	Research Techniques		
				W	O	SD
1	Environmental Analysis	a. Internal Environmental Analysis b. External Environmental Analysis	a. Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency (1.1) b. Madrasah Supervisor of the Ministry of Religion of Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Districts c. MAN Head d. Deputy Chief of Staff MAN e. Teachers' Council	√	-	√
2	Strategic Planning	a. Vision and mission planning b. Objective c. Strategic planning formulation	a. Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency b. Madrasah Supervisor of the Ministry of Religion of Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency c. MAN Head d. Deputy Chief of Staff MAN e. Teachers' Council	√	-	√
3	Strategic Implementation	a. Preparation of action plans b. Target c. Delegation of authority d. Staff mobilization e. Teacher development steps f. Coordination g. Communication	a. Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency b. Madrasah Supervisor of the Ministry of Religion of Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency c. MAN Head d. Deputy Chief of Staff MAN e. Teachers' Council	√	√	√
4	Strategic Control	a. Create benchmarks and performance measures b. Measure performance and relate required information c. Interpret information and take corrective action	a. Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency b. Madrasah Supervisor of the Ministry of Religion of Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency c. MAN Head d. Deputy Chief of Staff MAN e. Teachers' Council	√	√	√
5	Strategic Evaluation	a. Control system b. Evaluation techniques c. Evaluation analysis d. Evaluation results e. Follow up	a. Head of Madrasah Education, Ministry of Religion, Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency b. Madrasah Supervisor of the Ministry of Religion of Kotawaringin Timur and Pulang Pisau Regency (1.2) c. MAN Head d. Deputy Chief of Staff MAN e. Teachers' Council	√	√	√

Note: (W) Interview, (O) Observation, (SD) Documentation Study

C. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Strategic management of madrasah principals in improving the performance of Kotawaringin Timur MAN teachers

a. Analysis of the social and institutional external environment

Based on the findings, MAN Kotawaringin Timur is the only state madrasah in Kotawaringin Timur Regency, which will certainly attract MTs/SMP graduates. In an increasingly competitive educational environment, MAN Kotawaringin Timur certainly does not remain silent by planning and analysing the current conditions and situations, as well as the strategies taken to maintain the community's trust.

This can be seen from the community's high interest in including their children. At MAN Kotawaringin Timur. Furthermore, MAN Kotawaringin Timur externally, including (1) the existence of open space for educational institutions to develop themselves optimally; (2) support from the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia in the form of better policies and finances; (3) public appreciation for MAN Kotawaringin Timur is increasing; and (4).

There are opportunities for madrasa graduates to continue to prestigious universities at home and abroad. Meanwhile, the threats from MAN Kotawaringin Timur include: (1). the emergence of private madrasahs managed by the community or superior state schools as competitors; (2) the environment outside the madrasah is less educative; (3) public policies that have not placed education as a priority in development; (4) MAN Kotawaringin Timur has not yet become the main choice for some people; and (5) inconsistency of government policies in the education sector.

b. Analisis lingkungan internal: sumber daya pendidik, kebijakan dan strategi

Based on the findings, the internal environment of the madrasah is a very important component of the continuity of education. The organization at MAN Kotawaringin Timur will certainly run well by placing the right educational resources.

Policies and strategies by planning the goals of the madrasah appropriately, using a participatory approach involving various parties, including teachers, students, parents of students and the community. Due to MAN Kotawaringin Timur's commitment to implementing a curriculum based on the National Education Standards Agency (BSNP) standards, students' learning load is in accordance with BSNP standards. To improve the quality of graduates based on ANBK, students are given additional learning enrichment from class X to class XII.

There is local content in information and communication technology (ICT) development. Personal development is provided through counselling guidance, study clubs, and skills development clubs (theatre, scouts, da'wah, BDI, music, English Conversation Club, journalism, PMR, KIR, Olympic clubs, choir, nasyid, etc.). The education calendar at MAN Kotawaringin Timur refers to the National Education calendar.

c. Strategic planning

Based on the findings, strategy or strategic formulation determines programs or plans to be implemented in madrasas, formulated in deliberation by the Head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur and the deputy head of the madrasah, teachers and education staff. The final goal to be achieved is designing a strategy as an initial stage for the madrasah, establishing a vision and mission, accompanied by in-depth analysis regarding internal and external factors of the madrasah and setting long-term goals which are then used as a reference for creating alternative madrasah strategies, then one of them will be selected to be determined, according to madrasah conditions.

The analysis carried out by the institution is related to an in-depth understanding of the company's internal and external conditions or circumstances by clearly identifying factors in the form of internal madrasah strengths and weaknesses as well as opportunities that arise from the organization's external environment. This analysis aims to see the influences that will emerge from these factors on the goals or objectives of the madrasah so that the madrasah can appropriately consider the strategic policies that will be used.

d. Strategic implementation

Based on the findings, improving the quality of education is currently a concern for all parties, and it is important to consider improving it. Quality education is kept from the government's attention through training and support, both moral and material, as one of the government's extensions is to decide and appoint madrasa heads who have adequate educational qualifications and experience. The strategic management of madrasah heads plays an important role in achieving goals.

The efficiency of the achievement process depends on the strategic implementation of the organization's management. Strategic implementation has a significant role in achieving goals. Likewise, in the world of education, improving the quality of education is greatly influenced by the implementation of effective and efficient strategic management.

Strategic implementation is carried out by the head of MAN, Kotawaringin Timur, with his inherent leadership qualities and all his abilities, including ensuring the availability of adequate infrastructure, a comfortable learning environment, a learning curriculum that is appropriate to the surrounding conditions, professional teachers who carry out their duties with full responsibility, as well as making madrasah administration easier. As explained above, teachers have different tasks that.

e. Strategic control

Based on the findings, there are four ways to monitor and control the quality of education at MAN Kotawaringin Timur: (1) direct supervision by the head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur and by the supervisor of MAN Kotawaringin Timur. (2) Indirect supervision and control by the head of the madrasah because the head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur's duties are very complex. (3) Control based on exceptions. (4) Internal control and external control. The head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur carries out direct control in the form of control carried out directly by the head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur personally. Checking

the work being carried out by teachers and education staff to determine whether the implementation process and results are in accordance with predetermined standards and teacher performance.

Indirect control is carried out by the head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur, who has a very complex task. It is impossible to carry out as much direct control as possible, so this control task is carried out by indirect or remote control through reports provided by subordinates. Strategy and control in improving teacher performance at MAN Kotawaringin Timur are planned, systematic, measurable and controlled actions in achieving the expected goals.

This suggests that the strategic actions and control of madrasah heads in improving teacher performance have been successful, proven by the involvement of all educational components in an institution, starting from the leadership (madrasah heads and their deputies), teachers, staff/employees (educational personnel), students, as well as stakeholders.

The head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur, in this case, occupies a strategic and important position in efforts to formulate strategic actions while controlling all institutional activities and the performance of his subordinates in achieving the goals that have been set to improve the quality of education.

f. Strategic evaluation

Based on the findings, improving madrasahs' quality depends on the madrasah head's leadership. The head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur is alert to madrasah problems, starting with problems with students, teachers, education staff, facilities and infrastructure, curriculum, etc. The head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur also understands the advantages and disadvantages of madrasahs and then understands the opportunities and challenges of madrasahs in the future.

Identifying problems in madrasahs is very important for madrasah heads to carry out. So that you can understand and get solutions to resolving madrasah problems. Teacher performance is the result obtained after carrying out quality learning tasks. The teacher's performance in teaching and learning activities in the classroom has met the requirements of a professional teacher by looking at the learning tools created and the learning media that is applied during the learning process.

Evidence of certification data obtained by several teachers proves the teacher's professionalism in leading the learning process. Based on the findings, strategic evaluation is a way to determine the obstacles and results of implementation. In terms of improving teacher performance, the Head of MAN Kotawaringin Timur provides opportunities for teachers to take part in activities that have a positive impact on teacher professionalism, such as participation in seminar activities, training, teacher deliberations per region and subject teacher deliberations (MGMP), learning media workshops.

2. Strategic Management of Madrasah Principals in Improving Teacher Performance at MAN 1 Pulang Pisau

a. Environmental analysis

Based on the findings, MAN 1 Pulang Pisau's position in the internal and external environment is strong, with the public's high interest in registering their children at MAN 1 Pulang Pisau. Strategies that can be implemented by the head of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau to continue to gain the trust of the community include:

- Making plans and goals for the madrasah appropriately.
- Using a participatory approach.
- Having competent teachers.
- Creating a conducive madrasah environment.
- Providing madrasah facilities and infrastructure that are needed.

Based on the internal environmental analysis findings, including teacher resources, policies and strategies, for example, related to the curriculum, teachers, students and others, the external factors are social factors (society), government and related parties. An Islamic educational institution must, of course, know its problems and strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats so that it can produce brilliant solutions and lead Islamic educational institutions to a very influential position in the scientific struggle of the nation and the world.

The MAN 1 Pulang Pisau strategy formulation process cannot be separated from environmental analysis, both internal and external environments. This will make it easier to formulate a strategy, such as determining the right drug prescription once the disease is known. Some of the strengths that MAN 1 Pulang Pisau has regarding internal environmental analysis include: (1) providing dominant religious material; (2) educating students with morals and example; (3) training students to be independent, skilled and have a leadership spirit; (4) the madrasah environment is calm and strategic; (5) committee contribution fees are affordable according to the work and abilities of the student's parents; and (6) teachers are people who are competent in their field.

b. Strategic planning

Based on the findings, strategic planning in preparing the vision, mission and objectives of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, namely the vision and mission, is a very important element. Where vision, mission and goals are used in operations to move along a mutually agreed path and hope to achieve the desired conditions in the future.

The vision of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau has been future-oriented for a long period to show the hope of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau in a much better future, according to the norms and expectations of society, so that it can reflect the standards of excellence and ideals to be achieved and shows a strong drive for inspiration, enthusiasm, and a strong commitment to the development of the madrasah, able to become the basis and encourage change at

MAN 1 Pulang Pisau in a better direction, becoming the basis for formulating the mission and goals of the new madrasah. On the other hand, several components must be considered in improving the performance of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau teachers.

The components for the MAN 1 Pulang Pisau teacher performance plan include goals, performance indicators and targets to be achieved in the relevant period, programs to be implemented, performance indicator activities and expected targets in an activity. Therefore, the head of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau must utilize existing human resources to formulate effective and efficient formulations to improve the quality of education at the institution he manages.

c. Strategic implementation

The three elements of strategic management that are most difficult to implement to improve teacher performance are strategic implementation. The strategic implementation process in madrasa management includes all managerial activities, including motivation, compensation, management rewards and the supervision process. So that the program implementation process can run as expected, there must be an appropriate controlling system. The Head of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau must be able to carry out this role as well as possible, and this is accompanied by the implementation of targeted coaching based on the results of the notes obtained during the implementation of the controlling function. In the strategic implementation process of improving the performance of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau teachers, of course, there are responsibilities given to teachers, the method of giving responsibility or authority must be proportional, and the Head of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau provides clear guidance in the form of a decision letter or letter of assignment, as well as there is regular monitoring of whether the objectives of the activity are increasing or not.

The performance of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau teachers is very important to pay attention to and evaluate because teachers carry out professional duties, meaning that tasks can only be carried out with special competencies obtained through educational programs. Teachers have responsibilities that can be broadly grouped, namely, teachers as teachers, teachers as mentors, and teachers as class administrators.

The responsibilities carried out by the head teacher of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau as a leader to carry out the professional development of teachers to improve teacher performance, namely supervision carried out by the head of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, the supervisor of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, the office of the Ministry of Religion, Pulang Pisau Regency, to improve the quality of teachers, the Subject Teacher Conference (MGMP) program which is planned and carried out regularly continuously and sustainably, the madrasah carries out planned, effective and continuous supervision activities, the Head of MAN 1 Pulang Pisau can motivate and provide opportunities for teachers to participate seminar or workshop activities and upgrading in fields related to the expertise of the teacher concerned by bringing in relevant experts.

d. Strategic Control

The head of the madrasah assigns a role with a direct command pattern to his subordinates if important things must be carried out in the line of work below him. This is done so that the technical implementation of important work is consistent with the goals of the madrasah. The leadership role in this command form appears as a form of decision-making at MAN 1 Pulang Pisau. So that between leaders and subordinates, there are no hierarchical barriers.

Furthermore, in carrying out control, the Head of MAN 1, Pulang Pisau, has created benchmarks and performance measures, including those in the Teacher PK (Performance Assessment) document related to teacher competency. Measuring teacher performance includes the process of orientation, induction and assessing new teachers or teachers who are new to certain positions, assessing teachers who are experienced in their positions, and offering professional growth options for worthy teachers. Internal actors that influence teacher performance include motivation, positive emotions, negative emotions, responsibility for tasks, discipline in completing tasks, concern for students and job satisfaction.

e. Strategic Evaluation

Based on the findings, an evaluation of a madrasa head can determine the various obstacles faced during the strategy implementation process. If this process is carried out regularly, implementation will run according to the goals. So that the evaluation can run effectively. So, a leader must get clear, precise feedback from his subordinates in the madrasah. The technique in evaluating teacher performance is formulating references and criteria for teacher performance, then the madrasa head carries out a performance assessment, matches the assessment results with performance and then prepares recommendations or actions to be implemented. In mapping the strategy evaluation, it is divided into three stages.

The first stage is performance measurement. Performance measurement includes activity performance, which is the level of target achievement (planned achievement level) of each teacher; activity performance indicators; target achievement level, which is the level of target achievement (planned achievement level) of each target indicator that has been determined as in the performance plan document. The second stage is performance analysis and evaluation, which aims to determine the progress of the realization of the resulting performance, as well as the obstacles and challenges faced in achieving performance targets.

D. DISCUSSION

1. Environmental Analysis

Educational institutions (such as schools/madrasas) are a form of organization because we can also find the elements of organizational formation in educational institutions. The internal environment consists of three supporting elements, namely: first, structure,

relating to communication, authority and workflow. The structure is often also called a chain of command and is depicted graphically using an organization chart; second, culture is a pattern of beliefs, expectations and values that prevail among members of an organization. Values in an organization specifically give rise to and define behaviour acceptable to all members of the organization, from management to operations; and third, resources, including a person's skills, abilities and managerial talents from each member of the organization. Meanwhile, the external environment is conditions outside the organization that influence the organisation's continuity, such as the occurrence of protests or strikes, the emergence of changes in laws, environmental uncertainty and so on.

2. Strategic Planning

After analyzing external and internal environmental factors, the opportunities, advantages, weaknesses and threats in improving teacher performance at MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau are. The head of the Madrasah Aliyah plans the strategy formulation stage by formulating the organisation's vision, mission, goals and objectives. The head of the Madrasah Aliyah, in an effort to improve teacher performance both at MAN Kotawaringin Timur and MAN 1 Pulang Pisau, of course, there is a lot that must be prepared.

3. Strategic Implementation

In implementing or implementing the strategic direction of the head of the Madrasah Aliyah in improving teacher performance, the Madrasah must avoid management practices that are detrimental to everyone. Every decision or policy must be based on short-, medium- and long-term views. If only based on the short term, it will certainly be detrimental to the madrasah aliyah organization. Teachers have various duties or responsibilities, so teachers need support from the head of the madrasah aliyah in carrying out their duties and responsibilities. If the head of the Islamic school does not pay serious attention to the teacher's performance, the teacher will face difficulties in completing the various tasks they carry out.

4. Control

Performance measurement can be carried out in various activities, including process stage activities and results stages. These activities can be divided into three measurement objective criteria: administrative objectives, supervision or counselling, and research.

The data obtained can be used to validate selection procedures, program evaluation, and motivation evaluation and performance satisfaction. To obtain performance information, there are various conceptual and operational approaches, namely through performance measurement, which includes three dimensions to classify measurement forms, including measurement time, measurement specifications, and measurement indicators at the organizational level. The measurement period means that performance measurement results can be obtained immediately after the work behaviour is completed or later.

The measurement specification dimension means that the measurement is focused on the specification aspects of a performance or is based on overall work value. Meanwhile, the indicator dimension is a classification approach to measuring the closeness of organizational goals.

5. Strategy evaluation

Evaluation technique means the tools used to carry out evaluation activities. Various kinds of assessment techniques can be carried out in a complementary manner (complement each other) according to the competency being assessed, evaluation assessment techniques so that they can assist the Head of Madrasah in reviewing the implementation of tasks carried out by teachers.

E. CONCLUSION

The strategic management of the head of the Madrasah Aliyah has been carried out based on strategic management principles even though complete data have not supported it, so the institution's goals have not been achieved holistically. In addition, the strategy to realize the madrasa vision is not yet supported by an organizational structure and Standard Operating Procedures (S.O.P.), as well as strategic planning instruments that focus on achieving the goals of M.A.N. Kotawaringin Timur and M.A.N. 1 Pulang Pisau. In particular, this research also found that (1) The environmental analysis carried out by the Madrasah Aliyah was based on the principles of environmental analysis. However, its implementation was incomplete due to limited resources, especially human resources for teaching staff. (2) Strategic planning in improving teacher performance at M.A.N. Kotawaringin Timur and M.A.N. 1 Pulang Pisau is by using S.W.O.T. analysis and has also formulated a vision, mission, goals, targets, strategies and policies, although not perfect, but superior in M.A.N. Kotawaringin Timur and M.A.N. 1 Pulang Pisau are supported by a value system, namely theology, which is reflected, among other things, in the qualities of monotheism, manners and morals, Islamic law, and sincere values in work. (3) Strategic implementation of the head of the Madrasah Aliyah at M.A.N. Kotawaringin Timur and M.A.N. 1 Pulang Pisau has implemented the principles of strategic management evaluation, however, in terms of the availability of teacher resources, teachers are still hampered by low motivation to develop and improve their performance. (4) Strategic control of the head of the Madrasah Aliyah in improving teacher performance is carried out with guidelines on the main duties and functions of the head of the madrasah as manager and supervisor. However, control is more of a formality and has not touched on efforts to improve teacher performance at M.A.N. Kotawaringin Timur and M.A.N. 1 Pulang Pisau which actually. (5) The strategic evaluation of madrasah principals in improving teacher performance has been carried out based on the Teacher Performance Assessment, but this evaluation has not been used as a guideline for improving teacher performance at M.A.N. Kotawaringin Timur and M.A.N. 1 Pulang Pisau on an ongoing basis.

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